

LITERARY GENRES

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Abstract: These article In Uzbek literary studies, too, special attention was paid to the study of artistic and aesthetic research in Uzbek lyricism of the 70s and 90s of the 20th century in continuous connection with qualitative changes in the period and literary process, the personality of the poet, the psychology of society and the structural construction of lyrical genres.

Keywords: modern, principle, research, emergence, lyrical, direction, poetry.

In modern world literary studies, the principle of researching the issue of the role of creative artistic skills in the formation of literary genres and the emergence of new lyrical forms in direct connection with the evolution of poetic thought has intensified. As a result of scientific conclusions drawn on the basis of research of such directions as metarealism, continualism, polystilistics, which expressed updates in poetry, it was found that the advanced experiences of world literature and the creative appropriation of artistic cultural achievements expanded the scope of poetic forms in National Poetry. The creative experiences of the literature of the peoples of the world, the poetic genre and poetic forms enriched artistic thinking with new content and opened up new possibilities for expressing the national self. In this way, the lyrics, a current type of literature, were mobilized to respond in an artistic way to the issues advanced through social views and spiritual and intellectual values inherent in the life of the Uzbek people, to seek solutions.

Due to the deepening of the theory of artistic analysis in World Literary Studies, the directions of structuralism, comparativistics, receptive aesthetics, poststructuralism, narratology and hermeneutics are widely developing. The result

proved that World Poetry of the last quarter of the 20th century underwent a process of synthesis of various literary genres, and literature of a modernist and postmodernistic orientation was the basis for the widespread popularity of Quaternary, figure-eight forms and poetic series. Such evolutionary poetic updates in artistic-aesthetic thinking naturally caused structural-structural changes to occur even in the nature of traditional forms and genres of lyrics.

Thanks to the benefits and opportunities of independence in Uzbek literature, the phenomenon of improvement, perspiration, which is currently decided in the ideological and artistic content of national literature and in all its genres, is becoming more and more widespread. These features are also characteristic of the poetic forms of the 70s and 90s of the 20th century. Uzbek poets have also tried strength in genres of European lyric such as sonnet, epitaph, octave, tersina, Triolet, Elegy, and in genres such as Chinese, Japanese poetry such as hokku, tanka. As a result, artistic harmonious samples were created that enrich the treasure of our poetry. Uzbek poetry, which serves to elevate the spirituality of our people, is characterized by its focus on noble goals and its own characteristics. Because, "...it became even more clear that fiction, which is" an inimitable word that reflects the soul of a person, his troubles, the aspirations of the people, feelings of love and loyalty to the Motherland, is a magnificent mirror of knowing the world, man, as well as an important tool for raising a highly spiritual, comprehensively harmonious generation, which today is considered one of the strategic program.

In world literary studies, such issues as artistic-aesthetic research in lyricism, the period and literary process, the personality of the poet, the psychology of society and qualitative changes in the structural construction of lyrical genres are seriously studied

In Uzbek literary studies, too, special attention was paid to the study of artistic and aesthetic research in Uzbek lyricism of the 70s and 90s of the 20th century in continuous connection with qualitative changes in the period and literary process, the personality of the poet, the psychology of society and the structural construction of lyrical genres. Including academic N.In Karimov's article "poetic forms and

methodological directions" Mirtemir, S.Akbar, T.Interpretation and methodological features of folklorism in the work of Solomon, Otayor, A.Mukhtar, Mirmuhsin, E.Research of Vohidov and other poets in aruz, M.Shakhzade, R.Bobojan, Shukrullah's skill as a ruboiynavis, B.Owl and R.Parfi's experiences in the sonnet genre had been explored . Later, the problem of genres and poetic forms in Uzbek lyrics began to be studied much more widely. This issue became the basis for the emergence of a number of doctoral dissertations .

Theoretical issues such as tradition and novatorism in Uzbek poetic culture, poetic skill, artistic thinking and the individual style of the creator, philosophy, historicism, the deep roots of psychologism, updates in the nature of poetic thinking, poetic logic and artistic detail, plot and composition, Ghazal poetics, verbal and poetic image were also studied in a number of candidate dissertations .

It seems that the question of poetic forms and the role of creative individuality in the development of poetic thought in the Uzbek lyrics of the 70s and 90s of the 20th century has not been specially studied, and our research does not repeat the scientific work created so far. In terms of the choice of the topic, its approach, observation, scientific analysis and theoretical generalizations-conclusions, scientific work differs from existing research.

The fact that the last years of the last century have resolved the issue of studying the interaction of Poetic Forms within Uzbek lyricism, observing their peculiarities of enriching each other artistically aesthetically, revealing the place and significance of our poetry in the historical development, and establishing the ideological and aesthetic thinking and creative individuality of poets on this basis

The purpose of the monograph is to study the changes in internal quality and structure inherent in the nature of Uzbek lyricism of the pre-Independence years, to determine the artistic identities of poetic forms, to determine their properties as a holistic artistic-aesthetic system. Monograph tasks:

determination of common and different aspects of qualitative changes and methods of expression, brought into the structure of poetic forms according to the specific artistic thinking of creators;

highlighting the improvement of poetic forms on the basis of revealing the artistic and aesthetic essence of the textual-structural changes that occurred as a result of the development of a new ideological content due to the culture of thought and image of the four, which has taken a leading position in our classical lyrics, and the worldview of the creators;

associative (taxayyulli) as well as symbolic-emblematic artistic thinking influenced by the interrelationship of the Quaternary, the octave, the poetic series and other poetic forms and the definition of the processes of enrichment on the basis of comparison;

determination of the artistic and aesthetic laws of the expansion of the genres of Uzbek lyricism and the possibilities of poetic forms of the 70s and 90s of the 20th century, influenced by the methods of epic expression;

the principles of epicness in the nature of poetic series and the identification of epic image elements and the disclosure of the specific artistic skill of the creator in the development and enrichment of the culture of realistic image.

This article is intended for students of the philological Faculty of pedagogical universities and institutes, teachers of general literature and those who aim to study Uzbek lyrics in depth. We hope that the article will closely help literary scholars who aim to study the changes in internal quality and structure inherent in the nature of Uzbek lyrics, identify the artistic identities of poetic forms, study their properties as a holistic artistic and aesthetic system.

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